

Thrombectomy in Emergency Medical Science

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Received February 21. 2017, Accepted March 13. 2017

Abstract

Stroke is the major cause of disability and the third leading cause of death among the adult population in Poland. Scientific studies have reported that approx. 60 000 Poles suffer a stroke each year. Approx. 80% of strokes are ischemic strokes. In 1980, the World Health Organization (WHO) has identified stroke as a clinical syndrome characterized by the sudden onset of focal or generalized brain dysfunction, the symptoms of which last longer than 24 hours or are leading to death and have no other cause than vascular one. In recent years, in order to restore patency in the clogged vessel supplying blood to the brain, the thrombolytic therapy with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rtPA) or streptokinase. This method, however, has a number of contraindications, therefore thrombectomy is an opportunity for those patients who are not eligible to apply thrombolysis. Thrombectomy is currently used only in patients with ischemic stroke in the 6 hour therapeutic window. It involves mechanical removal of the blockage using a catheter introduced into the cerebral vessels through the artery. The procedure is performed under angiographic control and takes about 40 minutes. This is a direct form of treatment of the disease, at its most advanced stage. Scientific reports say that nearly 90% of thrombectomy implementations is effective in case of acute stroke. Thanks to the progress of medicine, researchers aim at eliminating contraindications against qualifying a patient for thrombectomy treatment.

Keywords: stroke, thrombectomy, emergencies, neurology, cardiology, Medical Rescue Team

Introduction

Despite the enormous advances in medicine, stroke is still a significant threat to human health or life, it leads to unwanted consequences in the form of a wide range of disabilities and even to death. It is caused by the sudden stopping of blood supply to the brain, usually as a result of narrowing or complete closure of the lumen of

the vessel bringing blood. Signs and symptoms characteristic for the diagnosis of stroke are: drooping corner of the mouth, slurred speech, weaker arm and leg, visual disturbances, and even paralysis of one side of the body. A quick restoration of patency of the vessel is able to reverse the symptoms of stroke, reduce post-stroke mortality and reduce the risk of disability [8].

1. Fot. Signs and symptoms of stroke

Origins: <http://patient.info/blogs/sarah-says/strokes-spotting-the-signs>

Restrictions on the Use of Thrombolysis

In recent years, in order to restore patency of the blocked blood vessel of the brain, thrombolysis was used (streptokinase or rtPA). Thrombolysis, however, has a number of contraindications, such as a history of haemorrhagic stroke or stroke of unknown etiology, ischemic stroke within the last six months, trauma, or cancer of the central nervous system, a history of big trauma or surgery, head injury in the past three weeks, the bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract in the last month, coagulation disorders or aortic dissection. In all these cases, you should use another treatment, which is a safe method for the patient. You should also analyze the balance of risks and benefits should also be analyzed, if the patient had a transient ischemic attack (TIA) in the last six months, uses anticoagulants orally, is in the first week postpartum in case of women, the patient is after puncture in an area, where no pressure can be applied, and after post-trauma resuscitation, has hypertension resistant to drugs with systolic blood pressure above 180 mm Hg, advanced liver disease, endocarditis or active peptic ulcer disease. [1]

Thrombectomy Procedure

Thrombectomy is the latest method of treatment of stroke, used only in patients with ischemic stroke. The purpose of this method is to restore the flow in the narrowed or completely clogged blood vessel. The treatment consists of locating thrombo-embolic material which is blocking one of the major arteries carrying blood to the brain and mechanical removal of it, using a catheter, under the control of X-rays, through the femoral artery to the brain vessels. The catheter is introduced into the femoral artery, and then guided into the cerebral vasculature to the site of the blockage in order to mechanically remove the obstacle. [1]

It is a very effective method used in patients, in whom thrombolysis has not brought the expected results or who cannot be treated with this method because of contraindications. [2]

It can be used only in the acute phase of stroke, and therefore one should adhere to the 6 hour therapeutic window. The doctor has to make the decision to qualify the patient for this treatment. The treatment is carried out with the assistance of specialists in neurology, radiology, vascular surgery, anesthesiology, as well as internal medicine [4].

It is believed that thrombectomy is a method of high-risk, requiring the cooperation of an experienced team of specialists and the availability of equipment, so it

is feasible only in selected Centres for Treatment of Stroke, where you have a round-the-clock support of a neurologist, an interventional radiologist, a vascular surgeon, an anesthesiologist and an internist. An arterial damage and hematoma within the area of the performed surgery are the risks that it carries.

Thrombectomy can be performed only during the first 6 hours of the onset of symptoms, in connection with the decision to refer to the nearest Centre for Treatment of Stroke, so the decision should be taken already by the Emergency Medicine Team at the time of diagnosis of stroke symptoms. It is worth remembering that time is brain, and the effectiveness of the therapy decreases with every passing minute. A key role in the whole process of healing is played by Emergency Medicine Teams, which are responsible for the correct diagnosis of stroke and for the safe and fastest possible transport of the patient to the stroke treatment centre [6].

The use of thrombectomy allows for recanalization and restoration of blood flow in approx. 60% to 90% of cases. [5]

In patients, in whom thrombectomy is used, the chance of survival and full recovery increases from 27% to 40%. [3]

In the majority of the clinical trials thrombectomy was preceded by thrombolysis. None of the therapeutic methods of treatment of stroke does not give one hundred percent chance to return to full health, so you should provide access to a variety of modern methods and they can also be combined. The combination of mechanical methods with thrombolytic therapy can in some cases extend the therapeutic window. [4]

Contraindications Against the Use of Thrombectomy

Unfortunately, there are also contraindications against thrombectomy. The absolute ones include:

- intracerebral haemorrhage made visible in CT or MR,
- duration of signs and symptoms longer than 6 hours,
- platelet count less than 100,000/mm³,
- glucose <50 mg dl (2,8mmol/l) >400 mg/dl (22,2mmol/l),
- heparin within 48 hours before the onset of stroke and the APTT time longer than the upper limit of normal laboratory norms,
- clinical symptoms of SAH, even without the confirmation of changes in the CT scan,

- systolic blood pressure > 185mmHg or diastolic blood pressure > 110mmHg, which does not decrease after administration of blood pressure medications,
- haemorrhagic diathesis,
- oral anticoagulation treatment e.g with: warfarin or acenocoumarol at INR> 1.7,
- recent active life-threatening bleeding,
- hemorrhagic retinopathy, e.g., connected with diabetes,
- acute pancreatitis,
- bacterial endocarditis,
- pericarditis,
- traumatic CPR within last 10 days,
- childbirth,
- puncture of vessels inaccessible to pressure (subclavian vein or artery),
- cancer at high risk of bleeding,
- major surgery or major trauma in the last 3 months,
- severe liver disease with liver failure, cirrhosis, or portal hypertension. [7]

Relative contraindications include:

- low or rapidly retiring neurological deficit before starting the treatment,
- stroke starting with seizures,
- stroke assessed clinically as severe or diagnosed vast area of it,
- ischaemia visualized in CT or MRI,
- a previous stroke in patient with diabetes mellitus,
- previous stroke within the last 3 months, past or active central nervous system damage (cancer, aneurysm, surgical procedures including the opening of the skull). [7]
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Conclusion

Emergency medical workers should have a wide range of knowledge and skills on how to recognize the symptoms of stroke. The patient with the correct diagnosis of stroke should immediately be transported to the Centre for Treatment of Stroke that is properly equipped and has a team experienced in the treatment of stroke using thrombectomy. This time should not exceed 6 hours from the first symptoms. Numerous scientific studies have demonstrated the high efficacy of thrombectomy in the

treatment of ischemic stroke, and therefore it is believed that patients who met the eligibility criteria for thrombolysis should be referred to a stroke centre in order to quickly perform this particular procedure on them. An important role in this procedure is played by the staff of Medical Rescue Teams, which are required to appropriately diagnose, pre-treat and rapidly transport the patient, which in turn increases the chance to perform the procedure of thrombectomy.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.